

Possible futures for rural East Africa under a changing climate

The impacts of climate change will vary across the region according to a range of local factors. Which of these impacts could be felt in your community in these three different climates?

- **FUTURE 1** Much wetter, large increase in heavy rainfall and hotter
- **FUTURE 2** Increase in extreme rainfall and hotter
- **FUTURE 3** Much hotter and drier with more erratic rainy seasons

Examples of Climate Change Impacts

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